

MADRAS

D5.12 Communication Activities

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Executive summary

This deliverable details the communication activities that have been done from M1-M15 including, among others, the development of the project's visual identity, the design of digital dissemination and promotional materials and project website, the set-up of social media accounts and online activity, media relations and the production of the first project newsletter.

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List of abbreviations

<i>EUT</i>	<i>Eurecat</i>
<i>IME</i>	<i>In Mould Electronics</i>
<i>OLAE</i>	<i>Organic and Large Area Electronics</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>
<i>VCI</i>	<i>Visual Corporative Image</i>

Introduction

MADRAS is a 3-year research project that has the objective to demonstrate a materials-driven improvement of OLAE devices, developing a high-speed manufacturing methodology in a scalable competitive process, which is In Mould Electronics (IME).

The project also addresses the need for innovative and industrial manufacturing processes for the development of a robust series of plastronics products. Building on an already established technology as plastic injection will facilitate a faster up taking. In addition, the MADRAS project will validate new inks and printing methodology with two product demonstrators that will work as a fingerprint reader and a geo-tracking tag.

EUT is the partner leader of Task 5.7 Communication Activities, but all consortium partners are involved in them. Task 5.7 has the objective to create and provide all the communication materials needed for conveying the project to a broad group of users.

All the actions will consider the European Commission recommendations explained in the Participant Portal H2020 Online Manual section on project communication. (http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communication_en.htm).

Communication activities

1. Project's corporate visual identity image

At the beginning of the project, EUT developed MADRAS's **Visual Corporate Identity (VCI)**, aimed at properly aligning all communication materials across all the project's tasks. The VCI includes the project's logo, a Power Point template, Word document templates for project activities and a visual identity standards' guidebook, which defines and outlines how to use identifying elements pertaining to MADRAS.

See **D5.9 Visual Corporate Image** for more information and details of the Visual Corporate Identity designed and implemented.

Figure 1: MADRAS full colour logo

Stationery

Figure 2: View of some pages of the MADRAS Visual Corporate Image (VCI) manual

2. Public Website

The project website (www.madras-project.eu) was launched in June 2020 (M3), as defined in **Deliverable 5.10 - Public Project Website**, to serve as the main information platform for users interested in knowing more about MADRAS, displaying the project’s basic information, objectives, demonstrators, and expected results.

Figure 3: Current MADRAS website structure

The website has been updated with new information and specific sections, such as the “[Media](#)” page, which includes the project’s press release and a list of relevant articles featuring MADRAS and published in print and digital media and the “[Newsletters & Promotional materials](#)” section, including the first project’s newsletter done, a banner to facilitate the subscription and the different project promotional materials published. Additionally, the “[News & Events](#)” page has been updated with more news regarding the project, events in which partners had participated and some new blog posts written.

On the other hand, in the following months, a new section to allocate results will be created, including a dropdown menu to show all audio-visual materials produced, newsletters published, new promotional materials designed, scientific production or new media articles, for instance.

Regarding the bog posts, 2 articles coming from partners GenesInk and COC have been published on the “News & Events” website sections since the beginning of the project:

- “[Novel materials for consumer electronics market](#)” by GenesInk (April 8th): Blog post explaining GenesInk contribution to the project for advancing materials performance by developing advanced inks that will be implemented as Transparent Conductive Electrodes (TCE) and Hole Transport Layers (HTL), allowing the development of devices by printing techniques with increased robustness, while reducing their cost and environmental impact.
- “[Towards finding suitable organic materials for advanced printed electronic devices](#)” by COC (June 2nd): This blog post explains the work done for selecting the most suitable material arrangement for MADRAS organic photodetectors-based biometric sensor.

See D5.10 Project Website for more details about blog posts information and guidelines prepared for all partners.

Figure 4: GenesInk and COC blog posts published on the website

Figure 5: Examples of posts published on Social Media sharing the two blog posts

Partners are contacted before their deadline and the topic is discussed together to avoid any overlapping between entities. All articles are edited by EUT and include a picture and short bio of the authors to give proper edit. To guide partners a blog post guideline with recommendations has been produced (see Annex 1).

For the following months, the blog post calendar proposal will develop as the following:

PARTNER	Blog post 1	Blog post 2
GNK	April 2021	April 2022
COC	June 2021	June 2022
AWCP	July 2021	May 2022
UPA	August 2021	July 2022
EUT	September 2021	September 2022
TNO	July 2021	February 2022
UWL	November 2021	December 2022
ETR	March 2022	November 2022
UNE	January 2021	January 2023
TNG	September 2021	September 2022
ERC	March 2022	December 2022
INF	October 2021	October 2022

Table 1: Blog post calendar proposal

2.1 Analytics M1 - M15

The MADRAS website has Matomo installed on the platform’s back end to monitor all the traffic and obtain, every month, reports about the site’s performance.

Since its launch in M3 (June 2020), the website has received **1,049 visits**, **2,986 page visits coming from 601 users** and **3,2 actions per visit including page views, downloads, outlinks, and internal site searches** (*analysis based on M3 - website creation until June 2021*).

As for geographical and device traffic distribution, the majority of visits have come from Spain (denoting EUT’s own efforts disseminating and communicating it at the Spanish level). The following figure seems relevant also to show that MADRAS has impacted beyond EU borders.

Figure 6: Top 5 visitor location per num. of visits and visitor map (June 2020 - June 2021)

Concerning devices, most of the sessions have been established through desktop devices. As shown in Figure 5, top viewed pages include the homepage, the page about MADRAS project, the section with information about OLAE and a page devoted to the project’s demonstrators.

Figure 7: Top 5 most viewed pages and device types per visit

3. Promotional materials

EUT has produced and designed different types of promotional materials, including an info-sheet, two rollup versions, a trifold, a factsheet template, a poster layout, a general presentation and a video focused on project’s topics.

All the materials follow the MADRAS’ VCI guidelines and are stored digitally in the project’s internal repository, as well as on the project’s website for broader dissemination. Users can download them in the “[Newsletters & Promotional Materials](#)” section on the website.

These materials, that serve as MADRAS’ “business card”, will be regularly updated according to project’s developments.

Figure 8: Promotional materials published on the project’s website

A factsheet template has been created with the objective to share all relevant MADRAS’ deliverables on project’s website and also through the **Zenodo Community** in order to show results and impacts achieved by the project.

The info-sheet template will be used to share the following project’s deliverables, once submitted and validated:

- D1.4 - Optimised nanocellulose foil - 2 M18
- D1.5 - Optimised organic conducting inks - 2 M18
- D1.6 - Optimised inorganic semiconducting inks - 2 M18
- D2.3 - Printed materials and devices - 2 M20
- D2.4 - Development of IME and thermoforming - 2 M20
- D3.2 - Geo-tracking flexible tag M33
- D3.3 - Biometric photosensor M33
- D4.4 - Implementation of the industrialisation of IME M36

ADVANCED MATERIALS AND PROCESSING IN ORGANIC ELECTRONICS

Factsheet - DATE dd/mm/yyyy

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Introduction / Executive summary

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Methodology / solution description

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Conclusions / results

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HIGHLIGHTED SENTENCE:
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The project has received funding from the EU's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 862492

Figure 9: Deliverables' factsheet template

4. Audio-visual materials

Engaging audio-visual materials (e.g., videos) have been proposed to present the key aspects of the project. The videos produced within the project are published on the MADRAS website, the YouTube channel and promoted on all project channels (social media).

The proposed videos to be produced are:

- **M18 - Animated Video:** MADRAS animated video with motion graphics describing the project main objectives and expected outputs.
- **M22-M24 - Video capsules:** Short interviews to project partners about topics related to the project (novel materials developed, IME technology, methodology, demonstrators, etc.).
- **M24-M36 - Production Process MADRAS demonstrators:** Video of the production process of each of the products validated with MADRAS technology. Partners will be in charge of recording images during the products' production in their facilities, which will be edit and them.

- M20-M36 - Experiments, production processes: short videos produced by partners conducting MADRAS tests / experiments, production processes for social media.

4.1 Videos produced (M1-M15)

At M6 (August 2020), a video was produced by INF, with EUT support, showing preliminary results of in mould integration of a printed/coated flexible photodetector. This video has been shared through MADRAS' Twitter account, published in project's YouTube channel, and also included in the first project's newsletter.

This video shows the MADRAS project's preliminary results of In-Mould integration of printed/coated flexible photodetectors. The integration of printed electronics by use of thermoforming and injection moulding opens possibilities for fast, robust, and versatile processes with broad application potentials.

See the video [here](#).

Figure 10: View of the video produced and shared on YouTube channel

5. Social Media

EUT is managing MADRAS' social media accounts, including a Twitter profile ([@MADRAS_Project](#)) created at M1, a [YouTube channel](#) created at M4 and a [LinkedIn account](#) created at M14 (May 2021).

Partners are contributing to spreading the word through their corporate and personal Social Media channels, including Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, and Instagram.

5.1 Twitter

MADRAS' Twitter account is managed by EUT with the support of project partners for the correct management of the profile.

The project's main objective on Twitter is to raise awareness on flexible electronics, OLAE devices production processes, benefits and new materials allowing the development of devices by printing techniques with increased robustness, while reducing their cost and environmental impact, as well as promoting the project's methodology / industrial production process to key stakeholders and the broader audience.

Figure 11: MADRAS Twitter Profile

5.1.1 Analytics (M1 - M15)

A profile in Twitter Analytics has been activated in order to measure Twitter's and other data about the account activity. Progress until the end of the project will be reported in the interim progress reports.

MADRAS activity on Twitter is being tracked monthly by EUT. The following table shows the account performance up to M15 (June 2021). In June 2021, the MADRAS Twitter account counts with **105 followers** and has generated **203 tweets** and more than **55K impressions**.

MADRAS Twitter account	M1-M15
Followers	105
Total tweets	203
Twitter impressions	55,303
Mentions	32
Likes on tweets	283
Retweets	133

Table 2: MADRAS Twitter profile data (M1-M15)

Figure 12: View of Twitter Analytics panel

5.1.2 Strategy

At the beginning of the project, EUT has detailed a Social Media strategy to follow, which mixes marketing content, branding and influence actions in order to maximise MADRAS’ project impact and facilitate market uptake.

The different posts published include content curation with news and information related to project’s topics, events in which partners have participated, dissemination of consortium meetings, promotion of the newsletter sign-up form created, distribution of the promotional materials and the press release produced, and other news related to MADRAS, among others.

Deliverable 5.11 MADRAS Communication Activities explains and details the Social Media strategy and management policy.

Figure 13: Examples of tweets published on MADRAS Twitter profile

5.2 YouTube

The YouTube account was created in M4 (July 2021). [MADRAS YouTube Channel](#) has been used as a video content repository and its content links have been shared on social media and through MADRAS' website.

For the moment, the channel has **1 video published**. As mentioned in previous sections, this video gives a general overview about the MADRAS project and presents some preliminary results related to in mould integration of a printed/coated flexible photodetector.

At M15, MADRAS YouTube Channel has achieved more than **170 visualisations and 9 subscribers**.

Figure 14: MADRAS YouTube profile

5.3 LinkedIn

LinkedIn is a platform for the interaction among professionals to exchange experiences to improve their work placement. The channel allows users to create interesting groups around specific initiatives or projects, ask or answer questions, post or search for jobs, etc.

EUT has created a [MADRAS LinkedIn page](#) on M14 (May 2021), which will allow to connect the academic and industrial community. The content published on LinkedIn will be very similar to Twitter publications and will be based on project news, blog posts, achievements, events attended by partners, newsletters and reports or publications produced in the framework of the project.

Figure 15: MADRAS LinkedIn profile

Figure 16: Examples of posts published on LinkedIn MADRAS account

The LinkedIn account is being managed by EUT with the collaboration of all project’s partners who are able to propose contents to be distributed through this channel. Partners are welcomed to spread the word through their own corporate and personal channels by sharing the content published.

Contents published on MADRAS LinkedIn include:

- Blog posts produced and published on project’s website
- Partners’ participation in key events, fairs, and congresses on project topics
- News and achievements related to the project and published in MADRAS website
- Audio-visual and digital promotional materials
- Press releases
- Specific information related to the project’s topics that can be interesting to the industrial and academic community.

Publishing, as well as comments, answers and private messages will be managed manually in order to facilitate the removal of potential fake users or spam content.

The use of hashtags is highly recommended (the same as defined in the Twitter strategy in Deliverable 5.11 MADRAS Communication Activities).

Data on publications’ impact is being retrieved periodically from LinkedIn Analytics. Progress until the end of the project will be reported in the interim progress reports.

MADRAS LinkedIn profile	M15
Followers	27
Total posts	9
Likes & reactions	61
Shares	15
Impressions	1,907

Table 3: MADRAS LinkedIn profile data (M15)

5.4 Partners channels

Each partner transmits MADRAS news and results through their personal and corporate social media accounts (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, and Instagram), including press releases, news about events, promotional materials and other contents published previously on www.madras-project.eu or in MADRAS’ Twitter account.

At M15, partners have published 16 posts on social media, accounting for 105 likes and 14 retweets / shares.

Figure 17: Examples of partners' posts about MADRAS published on partners' accounts

6. Media relations

A press release with general information about the project and its consortium has been produced, which was distributed to all partners and adapted to several languages.

EUT has written this first press release with the inputs of all the project's partners, which have validated all the content before sending it to the media outlets.

The press release produced had an important impact on online and print media. As a result, MADRAS project has been featured in **10 Spanish and English media outlets at regional, national, and international level**, including OAE-OPE Journal, Printed Electronics World, La Razón, MundoPlast or Interempresas, among others. *See Annex 2 for a complete list of articles featuring MADRAS.*

- **Consortium press release:** [European consortium to test new materials and manufacturing processes for organic printed electronics](#)

Figure 18: Press release published on MADRAS website. See the full text [here](#)

Additionally, some partners have adapted and published the consortium press release in their corporate webpages. See a complete list of these publications at **Section 5 of D5.15 MADRAS Communication Materials**.

6.1 Press release plan

For the following months, the press releases calendar will develop as the following:

MADRAS press release plan		Partner responsible
M24	Novel materials developed	EUT, AWF, GNK, COC, UPA
M33	Geo-tracking flexible tag	EUT, UWL
M33	Biometric Photosensor	EUT, ERC
M36	Final press release project results	EUT

Table 4: Press release plan proposal

7. Newsletters

At M15 (June 2021), EUT as MADRAS Communication Leader has produced and sent the **first project's newsletter**, including general information about the project, its main objectives, and expected results as well as the latest blog posts published and a selection of media articles featuring MADRAS.

- MADRAS 1st Newsletter (M15) - [Read here](#)

Hello!

Welcome to the first newsletter of the [MADRAS project](#).

We took off in April 2020 with the aim to develop new materials and manufacturing processes for scalable mass production of organic electronics devices, also known as OLAE devices, integrated into plastic parts for accelerated time-to-market.

In this issue, you will be able to find about:

- What is MADRAS Horizon 2020 project, main objectives and expected results.
- MADRAS participation in the 5E project Digital Showcase
- In-mould integration of printed flexible photodetectors
- The latest articles on the development of advanced inks and printing materials for organic electronic devices
- A selection of media articles featuring MADRAS

We hope you enjoy reading our newsletter and invite you to check our website regularly, follow us on social media or contact us directly for more information at info@madras-project.eu.

MADRAS at a quick glance!

The [MADRAS project](#) is developing low cost and reliable materials for a high-volume production of flexible plastronic products.

The project has the objective to boost the production of Organic and Large-Area Electronics (OLAE) by establishing a high-speed manufacturing methodology based on In-Mould Electronics (IME) optimised with improved materials and inks.

MADRAS takes part in 5E project Digital Showcase!

MADRAS has joined the [5E project Digital Showcase](#), an online platform aiming at increasing visibility and new opportunities for European electronics products, specifically whose innovative character builds on the combination of Nano-Electronics, Flexible, Organic & Printed Electronics and Electronic Smart Systems. The platform also includes products based on novel technologies and tools developed in the context of funded projects at a regional, national or EU level.

[Find out more](#)

MADRAS in the news!

See below a brief selection of articles featuring MADRAS:

- [Nano inks with novel functionalities](#) - OAE, OPE Journal (November 2020)
- [European consortium test new materials for organic printed electronics](#) - Printed Electronics World (November 2020)
- [Dispositivos electrónicos orgánicos impresos, la alternativa al cobre y al silicio](#) (in Spanish) - La Razón (October 2020)
- [Eurecat investiga nuevos materiales para plastrónica](#) (in Spanish) - Mundoplast.com (October 2020)
- [Ensayan nuevos materiales y procesos de fabricación de dispositivos electrónicos orgánicos impresos](#) (in Spanish) - Interempresas (October 2020)

About MADRAS project

MADRAS is a European project funded under H2020 grant agreement No. 862492 developing new materials and manufacturing processes for a scalable

Figure 19: View of some sections of the first newsletter published

The MADRAS first newsletter has been disseminated via links on social media, direct *ad hoc* emails to professional contacts of the consortium partners and via browsing the MADRAS website, where all newsletter issues will be stored.

See Section 6 at D5.11 MADRAS Communication activities for more information and details regarding newsletters management, platform, content, etc.

Figure 20: MADRAS Newsletter published on the project’s website

Figure 21: Examples of posts published on LinkedIn and Twitter sharing the project’s newsletter

Newsletter analytics, such as open rate or click through rate, are **extracted through Mailchimp platform**. Statistics have been checked 3 days after sending the newsletter and have been analysed in order to see which articles worked best so we are able to improve the newsletter impact in the following issues.

The following table includes some data regarding the first project’s newsletter, which was sent to a total of **50 subscribers**.

MADRAS 1 st Newsletter	
Open rate	27,1%
Total opens	38
Clicks through rate	12,5%
Clicks per unique opens	46,2%
Total clicks	15
Successful deliveries	96%

Table 5: MADRAS 1st newsletter analytics

Top locations by opens

Czech Republic	18	56.3%
Spain	7	21.9%
USA	3	9.4%
Finland	1	3.1%
France	1	3.1%

Figure 22: MADRAS newsletter top locations by opens

MADRAS Newsletters	Month
2nd newsletter	M19
3rd newsletter	M25
4th newsletter	M30
5th newsletter	M33
6th newsletter	M36

Table 6: MADRAS newsletters calendar proposal

8. Partners' communication activities

From M1-15 of the project, partners have also done diverse types of communication actions in order to increase awareness about the project and disseminate it through a large audience. Some of these activities are the inclusion of the project's information on their corporate website and newsletters, publication of MADRAS's news on their social media channels, or the production of some promotional materials, among others.

Date	Partner	Type of dissemination action	Description	Type of audience	Link
April 2020	EUT	Newsletter	Inclusion of MADRAS information into EUT internal newsletter sent to all employees	Scientific & Academic Community	NA
May 2020	EUT	Inclusion project information on Website	Project page in EUT website	General Public	Link
July 2020	GNK	Inclusion project information on Website	Project page in Genesink website	General Public	Link
July 2020	INF	Video-visual/ audio-visual material	In-mould process video	Industry Community	Link
Oct 2020	TNG	Inclusion project information on Website	Project page in TGN website	General Public	Link
Oct 2020	AWCP	Press release	Post of MADRAS press release in the powercoatpaper.com news	General Public	Link
Oct 2020	GNK	Press release	Inclusion of MADRAS press release on Genesink webpage	General Public	Link
Oct 2020	TNG	Press release	Inclusion of MADRAS press release on TNG webpage	General Public	Link
Oct 2020	EUT	Press release	Inclusion of MADRAS press release on EUT webpage	General Public	Link
Nov 2020	EUT	Newsletter	Inclusion of MADRAS press release into the Advanced Cluster Materials Cluster	General Public	NA
Nov 2020	GNK	Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	Article in OPE Journal (pp 24-25) on GNK materials based on Ag NWs and WO ₃ Nano inks with novel functionalities	General Public	Link
Dec 2020	GNK	Participation to a Workshop	International Virtual Workshop on CRM Innovations Frontiers	Industry Community	Link
April 2021	EUT	Newsletter	Inclusion of a publication regarding MADRAS project review in the internal EUT newsletter sent to all employees	General public	NA
June 2021	EUT	Newsletter	Inclusion of MADRAS first newsletter in the internal EUT newsletter sent to all employees	General public	NA

Table 7: List of partners' communication activities (M1-M15)

Communication activities management

9. Communication KPIs

The following table introduces an initial set of MADRAS Key performance Indicators (KPIs) for assessing the communication activities. Progress until the end of the project will be reported in the interim progress reports.

Strategy	Indicator	Means of verification	M1-M15	Target by the end of the project
Media	Number of press releases	Proof of publication and reporting in reports / project meetings	1	>2
	Number of articles published		10	>30
Website	Number of web visits	Matomo Analytics	1,049	>4,000
	Number Pages Viewed		2,986	>10,000
	Number page / session		3.2	>1,5
	Number users		601	>2,000
	Avg. session time		4 min	>3,00 min (70% of the users)
Newsletters	Number of newsletters issued	Proof of publication in reports	1	6
Social Media - Twitter	Number Followers	Twitter Analytics	105	>200
	Number Tweets		204	>150
	Twitter Impressions		55,303	>50,000
	Number mentions		32	>20
Social Media - YouTube	Number of videos uploaded	Proof of publication in reports	1	>2

Social Media - LinkedIn	Number Followers	LinkedIn Analytics	27	>50
	Number Posts		9	>50
	Likes / Reactions		61	>100
Social Media - Partners	Number of posts in corporate channels	Monthly follow up (quantitative)	16	>20
	Number of Likes in corporate channels		105	>50
	Number Shares / Retweets in corporate channels		14	>10
	Participation in LinkedIn groups		0	Proof of publication

Table 8: Communication KPIs (M1-M15)

9.1 Communication Activities Calendar

COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26
MADRAS	jun-21	jul-21	aug-21	sep-21	oct-21	nov-21	dec-21	jan-22	feb-22	mar-22	apr-22	may-22
Update Twitter Account	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Website update	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
2 nd Newsletter					X							
Animated video				X								
Video interviews to partners for Social Media										X	X	X
Videos on production process MADRAS demonstrators										X	X	X
Videos on MADRAS experiments and production process										X	X	X
Press release materials developed												X
3 rd Newsletter											X	
	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36		
	jun-22	jul-22	aug-22	sep-22	oct-22	nov-22	dec-22	jan-23	feb-23	mar-23		
Update Twitter Account	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Website update	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Videos on production process MADRAS demonstrators	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Videos on MADRAS experiments and production process	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		

ANNEX

1. Media clipping (M1-M15)

Date	Media	Title	Typology	Link
09/10/20	Interempresas	Dispositivos electrónicos orgánicos impresos, la alternativa a cobre y silicio	Online	Link
11/10/20	Factoria del Futuro	Materiales y procesos de fabricación de dispositivos electrónicos orgánicos impresos	Online	Link
13/10/20	Mundoplast.com	Eurecat investiga nuevos materiales para plastrónica	Online	Link
14/10/20	Cerdanyola.info	Eurecat assaja nous materials i processos de fabricació de dispositius electrònics orgànics impresos	Online	Link
14/10/20	Revista Plásticos Modernos	Ensayan nuevos materiales y procesos de fabricación de dispositivos electrónicos orgánicos impresos	Online	Link
16/10/20	La Razón Digital	Dispositivos electrónicos orgánicos impresos, la alternativa a cobre y silicio	Online	Link
16/10/20	30virtual	Eurecat coordina un projecte europeu per desenvolupar nous materials i processos de fabricació de dispositius electrònics orgànics impresos	Online	Link
18/10/20	La Razón - Innovadores	ESCAPARATE DE IDEAS	Print	Link
05/11/20	Printed Electronics World	European Consortium Test New Materials for Organic Printed Electronics	Online	Link
10/11/20	OAE - OPE Journal	Nano inks with novel functionalities	Online	Link

Table 9: List of articles featuring MADRAS published in media outlets

